

Biomarkers in relation to low level of ionising radiation exposure

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Present review has focused on the ionising radiation induced biomarkers. These biomarkers were different biochemicals, biopolymers, enzymes, single cells, chromosomes etc. Ionising radiation dose is varied from few cGy to 50 Gy to bring about detectable changes in all the systems mentioned. For biochemical markers – their source, dose range, effect that is brought about by radiation dose have been mentioned. For enzymes also, their source, dose at which enzyme activity alters have been mentioned. For biopolymers – their origin, dose range within which response is linear at a particular dose rate have been mentioned. For single cells by microgel electrophoresis technique lysis condition, electrophoresis condition, measurement parameters and dose range have been mentioned.

Relatively recently different types of chromosomal aberrations, lymphocyte – dicentric assay, different types of DNA damages and DNA mutations, gene expression and protein expression changes etc. as induced by ionising radiation exposure have been used as biodosimeters. These all are in the cGy dose range. In recent times their importance have increased due to their medical and military utility and for accident dosimetry purposes.

Ionising radiation-induced damage to biological systems ultimately leads to cell death depending upon absorbed dose. Degree of sensitivity for radiation dose to different biological systems is in the following increasing order : Hemopoietic system (1–2 Gy) > Gastrointestinal system (5–10 Gy) > Central nervous system (20–50 Gy). While purely biological dosimeters deal with changes in cells and cellular constituents – *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *In vitro*, biological dosimeters and biochemical dosimeters deal with ionising radiation-induced changes in biomacromolecules and biochemicals. Dose required for a specific change in an *in vitro* system are generally more compared to that for an *in vivo* system for the same biochemical end point.

50 Gy of absorbed dose of radiation has been fixed as the upper limit as all the radiochemical, radiobiochemical and radiobiological changes are within this dose that has got biotechnological application, practical medical diagnostic utility or help in predictive assay. Low dose was defined as ranging from background radiation dose to as high as 700 mSv based on NATO and US military radiological guidance documents. There will be large number of biomarkers within this dose range. We will confine only to those biomarkers that have been proved clinically feasible and those that are potentially suitable for clinical use afterwards. Though there are reviews available in this area¹⁻³, in this communication we are confining only with some biochemicals, enzymes, nucleic acids, nucleoproteins and

some relatively new biomarkers that have been used as *in vitro* biomarkers either by us or has been reported.

Definition :

Biological changes that occur in a range of cellular, structural, molecular and genetic levels as a result of low levels (~50 Gy) of radiation are collectively called biomarkers⁴. The changes in the physico-chemical or biochemical or biomacromolecular or cellular properties should preferably be proportional to dose. So, quantitation in dose and response are essential.

Essential characteristics of biomarkers :

(i) There should be a proportional change in the properties of biomarkers with increasing radiation dose. The dose rate range of 0.007 Gy/s to 0.033 Gy/s is preferable. These properties can be absorbance, fluorescence, conductance, pH, optical rotation, chemiluminescence, lyoluminescence, etc. Other biochemical changes for nucleic acids, proteins, nucleoproteins and enzymes have been mentioned.

(ii) These should be measured in fluids, tissues or cells that can be easily obtained from experimental animals or humans beings.

(iii) It should be established whether the dose-response relationship is dose rate dependent or not. In case of dose rate dependency the dose rate range within which response is proportional to dose should be established.

Table 1. Characteristics of some biomarkers

Biochemical markers				
Biomarker	Source	Dose range (Gy)	Effect	Ref.
Cysteic acid, valine, leucine, hydroxyproline, phenylalanine, arginine, aspartic acid, proline, threonine, tryptophan, β -aminoisobutyric acid, 5-HTP, 5-HT	Human urine	0.3–4.10 Gy 0.37–4.10 Gy	Increase in the amino acid level by 20–30 fold	9, 56
Creatine	Urine	0.50–6.50 Gy of X-rays	Increase in creatine level is linear with dose	10
Deoxycytidine	Human urine Rat urine	Radiation therapy treatment 2–6.50 Gy	Marked increase in deoxycytidine level Increase in deoxycytidine with dose is linear	7
5-Hydroxyindoleacetic acid	Rat urine. Local irradiation of genital carcinoma	1 Gy	Increase in 5-HIAA	11

(iv) High signal to noise ratio.

(v) Stability of dose response relationship should be established.

(vi) Assays should be rapid and ultimately capable of automation.

Physical factors of energy deposition :

Physical factors that influence response are type of radiation, total energy deposition, linear energy transfer (LET), dose rate, dose distribution etc. For low LET radiation effectiveness for inducing biological damage decreases with decrease in dose rate for a given total dose. At very low dose rate the dose-response relationship is linear. But for high LET radiation effectiveness of biological damage increases with decrease in dose rate⁵. The different types of radiations have different penetrating powers. So, biological damages are also different for each type of radiation. For a given biological endpoint the effectiveness for different radiations is compared with 250 kV_p X-rays as standard. Some of the radiations are of particle type (e.g. α and n) and their interactions are largely confined on the surface. But β and γ -radiations in the form of beams penetrate the tissues to different extent depending upon their energy content, velocity in the tissues and attenuation in the tissues.

Non-uniform distribution of energy and mass of incident energy particles (e.g. α , β , γ , n) cause serious problems when using biological changes as an estimation of damage to calculate either dose or risk⁶.

Radiation induced endpoints pertaining to biochemicals, nucleic acids, proteins, nucleoproteins and enzymes :

Biochemicals :

For biochemicals the end points can be decarboxylation, deamination, desulphuration, formation of inorganic phosphorus, shortening of chain length and finally decomposition to smaller compounds.

Exhaustive work has been done on biochemical markers of ionising radiation. The amino-acids that increased in urine of human beings are deoxycytidine in urine⁷, β -aminoisobutyric acid⁸, taurine, cysteic acid, valine, leucine, hydroxyproline, phenylalanine, arginine, aspartic acid, proline, threonine and tryptophan. The dose range is 0.37 to 4.10 Gy⁹. The increase in the levels of amino-acids is 20–30 fold. For a dose range of 0.50 to 6 Gy of X-ray creatine level increases linearly with dose¹⁰. 5-Hydroxyindoleacetic acid level of urine increases in the local irradiation of patients¹¹.

For biopolymers the end points can be as follows :

Nucleic acids : Breakage of hydrogen bond, chain break, cross linking, disruption of sugar-phosphate backbone, formation of inorganic phosphorous, base damage, impairment of transforming ability, inability to act as a template for the synthesis of new strand etc.

Effect of radiation on DNA is dependent on dose, time and phase of cell cycle. In solution *in vitro*, above a dose of 10 Gy on DNA causes damage of the following types : breakage of hydrogen bond, chain break, cross linkage, disruption of sugar-phosphate backbone of DNA, impairment of transforming ability of DNA, DNA base damage, inability of DNA to act as a template for the synthesis of a new DNA strand.

As there are messenger RNA, transfer RNA and ribosomal RNA in mammalian cells most studies have measured the effect of radiation on total RNA synthesis. Be-

Table 2. Biopolymers/biopolymer complexes/drugs/drug-biopolymer complexes

Biomarker	Source	Dose range (Gy)	Effect	Ref.
Diltiazem (drug) (25 µg/ml)	Act on endothelial cells of cardiovascular system	Upto 4 Gy. dose rate 0.018 Gy/s	Linearity in dose response relationship at 240 nm	19
Diltiazem-DNA (5 : 10 µg/ml)	Acts on endothelial cells of cardiovascular system	Upto 10 Gy. Dose rate 0.018 Gy/s	Linearity in dose response relationship at 204 nm. and 270 nm	18
H ₁ -Histone (200 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 12 Gy. dose rates 0.0135 Gy/s and 0.0504 Gy/s upto 75 Gy at 2.25 Gy/s	Linear decrease in dose response relationship at 230 nm	58
H ₃ -Histone (50 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 50 Gy. Dose rate 0.0135 Gy/s	Dose response relationship remained unchanged	59
H ₃ -DNA (50 : 50 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 50 Gy dose rate 0.0106 Gy	Linear decrease in dose response relationship at 206 nm and 260 nm	59
H ₄ (200 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 75 Gy	Linear	32
H ₁ -DNA	Nucleosome	Upto 50 Gy. dose rate 0.025 Gy/s	Increase in absorbance at 206 nm and 260 nm in phosphate buffer and 226 nm and 260 nm in SSC buffer with dose	60
DNA (100 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 100 Gy. dose rate 0.0156 Gy/s	Depletion of inorganic phosphorus from DNA	61
DNH (200 µg/ml)	Nucleosome	Upto 100 Gy. dose rate 0.0156 Gy/s	Depletion of inorganic phosphorus from DNH	61
Biopolymer	Cells	Biopolymers in cell system Dose range (Gy)	Effect	Ref.
DNA	He-La cells, CHO cells	5.00-7.50 Gy	DNA synthesis rate maximally depressed (~50%) in S phase	11, 62, 63
DNA	Liver	15 Gy	DNA synthesis inhibited in liver after 24 h of irradiation	64
DNA	He-La cells human lymphocytes	50-100 Gy	Unscheduled DNA synthesis	65
DNA	Rat regenerating liver	15-30 Gy	Marked inhibition of DNA synthesis. No effect on RNA synthesis	66
RNA	He- La cells	10 Gy	RNA synthesis is depressed by 30 to 50%	67

cause of the complexities involved in RNA structure and function the effect of radiation on RNA is not completely known.

Proteins : Structural alteration, disulphide bond breakage, disruption of peptide bond, loss of chromophores and fluorophores etc.

Nucleoproteins : Dissociation to nucleic acids and proteins, followed by degradation of nucleic acids and proteins in various ways mentioned.

Enzymes : Either increase or decrease of enzyme activity due to change in conformation induced by radiation (increased activity) or loss of amino-acid residues (decreased activity) or radiation-induced destruction of the conformation of the active site of enzyme.

Irradiation of X-rays to mammalian cells increases the activity of some enzymes whereas it decreases in others. The dose-response relationship for enzymes varies with phases of cell cycle (e.g. monoamine oxidase to gamma rays), from one species to another¹², differences in the dis-

tribution of various cell types, age of species radiation dose, time of assay, nutritional status, P/O ratio (i.e. inorganic phosphorus/available oxygen in the tissues or cells), presence or absence of trace metals (e.g. Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn etc.) as co-factors of enzymes. Mostly enzymes are radiosensitive upon induction of radiation but after completion of synthesis they become highly radioresistant.

Molecular techniques :

The following techniques namely cell growth characteristics, cell metabolism, cytogenetic analysis, direct measurement of DNA damage, single cell microgel electrophoresis, chromosomal aberration and gene expression are gaining importance in recent times.

(a) It is possible to monitor changes in individual types of DNA base damage at very low levels (0.05 Gy) following low levels of exposure as the lesions are lost otherwise¹³. For this purpose sample must be obtained very soon (minutes to hours) after exposure.

(b) Changes in gene expression have been detected following low level of exposure to radiation. But the changes are transient and so may play an important role in adaptive response¹⁴.

(c) Changes in multiple genes can be detected by multiple gene chip technology¹⁵. This may be very important in risk assessment and understanding the response of cells and tissues to very low doses of radiation.

In vitro biological dosimeters developed at INMAS :

Biochemical dosimeters :

Some biochemicals namely 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5-HTP) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) at a concentration of 90.82 μM and dose rate of 0.077 Gy/s showed linearity in response up to 1500 Gy. Absorbance values at 275 nm and 207 nm (λ_{max}) and shoulder at 220 nm for both these compounds were measured and A_{unirr}/A_{irr} values plotted against dose. Both these compounds at this completely non-toxic level can be used as *in vitro* biochemical dosimeters. So, the response is definitely linear up to 50 Gy. As has been discussed earlier absorbed dose *in vitro* is always greater than that *in vivo*. Both 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5-HTP) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) are neurotransmitters and hence radiation induced changes in the neuronal fluid can be obtained by measuring changes in these two biochemicals. 5-HTP and 5-HT are considered in the functioning of different organs namely brain, kidney, heart, etc. under normal and stressed conditions. Their levels also vary with radiation dose in different organs^{16,17}. Hence these two metabolites can be used as *in vitro* biomarkers of ionising

radiation exposure. The dose range within which 5-HTP and 5-HT have shown linear dose-response relationship i.e. 1500 Gy and 500 Gy respectively at a dose rate of 0.077 Gy/s to 0.33 Gy/s. This will be important from radiobiological point of view (Table 1).

Biopolymers as in vitro dosimeters :

For Diltiazem : DNA complex (5 : 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) absorbance intensity increased with dose linearly up to 10 Gy at a dose rate of 0.018 Gy/s, pH 6.75 at 204 nm, 240 nm and 270 nm. The absorbance intensities were in the following decreasing order $A_{204 \text{ nm}} > A_{240 \text{ nm}} > A_{270 \text{ nm}}$. Diltiazem can be used as a marker for micronuclei formation up to 3 Gy and radiation induced cardiovascular degeneration up to 10 Gy when it is complexed with DNA^{18,19}. Diltiazem is a calcium channel blocker²⁰ and a cardiovascular therapeutic agent^{21,22}. It has been shown to protect wholebody irradiated mice against lethal dose. The cytoprotective effect of diltiazem has been demonstrated in bone marrow cells and haemopoietic stem cells²³. Diltiazem-DNA complex can be used as a biomarker of ionising radiation exposure up to 10 Gy *in vitro* up to a dose rate of 0.0185 Gy/s at pH 6.75¹⁹. For the endothelial cells located at bifurcations of the capillaries diltiazem functions for its cardiovascular therapeutic activity.

H₁ histone (conc. 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), pH 7.3–7.4, in 0.9% sodium chloride showed linearity in $A_{230 \text{ nm}}$ values up to 75 Gy at a dose rate of 2.25 Gy/s and up to 20 Gy at a dose rate of 0.0135 Gy/s. As H₁ histone is known to protect neoplastic human cell lines and erythroleukemic cells, this dosimeter can be used to detect radiation-induced onset of neoplasia and erythroleukemia²⁴ at the earliest incidence. Moreover, it is known that it acts as a repressor of transcription of DNA²⁵.

In $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ EDTA, pH 8.0, DNA (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) showed depletion of inorganic phosphorus as a linear function of dose from 10 Gy to 80 Gy. In the same solvent DNA (200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) also showed depletion of inorganic phosphorus from 10 Gy to 100 Gy at the same dose rate (i.e. 0.0156 Gy/s). So, DNA damage producing inorganic phosphorus can be used as a biomarker.

Both DNA and DNH are essential constituents of chromosome. Radiation-induced damage of DNA (conc. 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and DNH (conc. 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) at pH 8.0 producing inorganic phosphorus ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) have been found to show linearity in increase in P_i from 10 Gy to 80 Gy for DNA and 10 Gy to 200 Gy for DNH. As both these biopolymers are vital for cell survival these dosimeters can be used to indicate primarily chromosomal aberration²⁶ and finally cell

Table 3

Enzyme	Source	Enzymes Dose range (Gy)	Effect	Ref.
Thymidine kinase	Regenerating rat liver	15 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
DNA polymerase	Regenerating rat liver	15 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
Monoamine oxidase	Mouse and fish liver	20 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
Substrate induced tryptophan pyrrolase	Rat liver	60 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
L-Serine dehydrates	Rat liver	4–16 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
Dehydrogenase enzymes (succinic, α -glycerophosphate and lactate dehydrogenase)	Mouse testis	10 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
Δ^5 - 3β Hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase	Human placenta	2 Gy	Enzyme activity decreases	34
Alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphates, β -glucuronidase	Mouse testis	10 Gy	Enzyme activity increases	34
Δ^5 - 3β Hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase	Human placenta	10 Gy	Enzyme activity increases	34
Catechol- <i>o</i> -methyltransferase	Mouse neuroblastoma	6 Gy	Enzyme activity increases	34
Acetyl cholinesterase	Mouse neuroblastoma	6 Gy	Enzyme activity increases	34
Cholineacetyltransferase	Mouse neuroblastoma	6 Gy	Enzyme activity increases	34

death²⁷. So, both of them can be used as *in vitro* biomarkers at a dose rate of 0.0156 Gy/s.

DNA- H_1 complex in the concentration ratio of 4.17×10^{-9} ML⁻¹; 116.3×10^{-8} ML⁻¹ in phosphate buffer showed increase in absorbance intensity at 260 nm and 206 nm with dose up to 50 Gy at a dose rate of 1.5 Gy/min. The absorbance intensity values are more at 206 nm compared to that at 260 nm. In the same concentration ratio of DNA : H_1 for the same dose rate the complex showed increase in $A_{226\text{ nm}}$ and $A_{260\text{ nm}}$ with dose up to 50 Gy in SSC buffer. The $A_{260\text{ nm}}$ values are more compared to $A_{226\text{ nm}}$ values. This DNA- H_1 complex biomarker can be used for formation of erythro-leukemia as function of dose as H_1 histone is known to give protection to erythroleukemic cells. Normal and neoplastic human cells upon examination have shown that H_{1a} and H_{1b} in normal human cells is considerably lower than that in neoplastic cells and this ratio increases with the increased ability of the cells to form tumors in nude mice²⁴.

If ionising radiation induces the H_{1a}/H_{1b} to increase it will help in producing tumors. But if with radiation the ratio decreases it will regress the tumor size. So, radiation induced changes in H_1 histone is a biomarker of neoplastic²⁴ growth or regression. So, H_1 histone (200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) can be used as an *in vitro* biological dosimeter in 0.9% sodium chloride at pH 7.3–7.4 to 30 Gy at a dose rate of 0.0135 Gy/s and up to 75 Gy at a dose rate of 2.25 Gy/s.

H_1 histone reduces nucleosome mobility and thereby interferes with disruption or repositioning of nucleosomes that are required for transcriptional activation²⁸. Transcriptional activity will be modified by radiation as H_1 histone folding will be altered by radiation. So, radiation induced changes in H_1 histone are a marker for transcriptional activity²⁵.

The absorbance intensity of DNA : H_3 (50 : 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) complex at $A_{260\text{ nm}}$ decreased with dose up to 50 Gy but $A_{206\text{ nm}}$ values remained fairly constant for the same dose range at the dose rate of 0.0106 Gy/s in 0.9% sodium chloride, being a physiological solvent. The biological system for which it is suitable as a dosimeter is radiation induced ageing^{29–31}.

As 0.9% sodium chloride is a physiological solution, H_3 -DNA in the concentration ratio of 50 : 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ can be used as an *in vitro* biomarker of ionising radiation dose in the dose rate of 0.0106 Gy/s. The biological system for which it is suitable is radiation-induced ageing^{29–31}.

The primary focus of much current research is on how histone acetylation relates to the regulation of gene expression. Less attention is being paid on understanding the biological function of deposition related acetylation. All core histones are required to mediate extensive chromatin folding at physiological ionic strength.

H_1 histone (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) and H_1 -DNA complex (25 : 25

µg/ml) can be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeter up to a dose of 100 Gy at a dose rate of 0.0106 Gy/s in 0.9% sodium chloride solution in the physiological pH range of 6.70–7.00. H₄-DNA complex can be used as cytogenetic marker up to 100 Gy³².

H₄ histones are needed for interfiber interactions. This is mediated by acetylation. Genetic and biochemical approaches have shown the mechanistic connections between histone acetylation and transcription process³³. As a result of irradiation the acetylation may not take place to the required degree thereby affecting transcription process.

Characteristics of some biomarkers, their nature, source, dose range, effect that is produced as a result of irradiation etc. have been given (Table 2).

Enzymes :

Enzymes in solution state when irradiated by gamma irradiation with one or a combination of the reactive species (e.g H, e_{aq}⁻, OH⁰ etc.) get inactivated. The cause of inactivation may be conformational change, degradation of active site, destruction of some of the amino-acids or specific groups etc. Various types of enzymes respond differently to radiation. Table 3 will summarize some of the enzymes and their response to radiation dose³⁴.

Single-cell microgel electrophoresis :

Ostling and Johnson³⁵ first described the technique in which they mixed cells (murine lymphoma, L5178Y-S or Chinese hamster fibroblast, Cl-1) with melted low-gelling temperature agarose that was then layered on a microscope slide, ice chilled and immersed in a neutral cell-lysing solution for 1 h. High-molecular-weight DNA remained in the agarose-gel left by each lysed cell, other cellular material rapidly diffused through the gel into the lysing solution. During electrophoresis some DNA migrated from the cavity (or "head" region) towards the anode forming a "tail" region, which, when viewed using a x 100 objective, had a fibrous structure.

Singh *et al.*³⁶ modified the technique (the single-cell gel (SCG) assay) to examine the effect of low doses of X-rays. The SCG assay used high ionic strength NaCl in the lysis buffer to produce a cleaner, histone-free DNA and allowed the unwinding of DNA strands before electrophoresis. The technique was suited to detect single-strand breaks and the presence of alkali-labile sites. It was particularly sensitive to low dose of radiation (between 0.25 and 2 Gy there was an approximately linear increase in the length of the "tail" region) and few non-irradiated cells showed a migration of DNA. Above 2 Gy the increase in "tail" length appeared to

plateau, the DNA damage being too extensive to determine accurately the length of the tail. Repair of X-ray induced DNA damaged cells in suspension, after an incubation at 37°C, was assessed by embedding cells in a layer of agarose before lysis and electrophoresis. The bulk of the "repair" occurred rapidly (by 15 min), and a second slower component was "essentially complete by the end of the 120 min incubation period". A large number of dosimeters based on this principle have been shown in Table 4.

Practical clinical utility of "Comet assay" :

Basal damage in X-ray induced (2 Gy dose) DNA obtained from lymphocytes of young (<60 year) and old (>60 years) donors were compared by measuring average tail length. About 12% increase in the average length of tails in the older group was obtained³⁷.

5–10 µL blood obtained from a finger puncture was sufficient to detect differences in DNA migration pattern of peripheral blood lymphocytes³⁸.

T-Lymphocytes following UV_c irradiation showed a substantially increased level of strand breakage 1 h after irradiation. Cycling xeroderma pigmentosum lymphocytes had greatly reduced strand breakage. Strand rejoining rather than excision step of UV repair was defective in lymphocytes *in vivo*. This could be a rapid diagnostic tool for xeroderma pigmentosum³⁹.

Both radiation-induced and xenotoxic agent induced effects on DNA can be assessed by this technique (Comet assay)⁴⁰. This assay has the potential of prediction of patient's responses by their cell response and sensitivities to radiotherapy and chemotherapy.

Chromosomal aberration – different types, DNA damage – different types, gene expression :

Chromosomal aberration based bioassay is the gold standard for radiation biomarkers⁴¹. The lymphocyte-dicentric bioassay for radiation exposure assessment^{42,43} has been the subject of intense scientific interest⁴⁴. The commonly accepted threshold for typical applications of the lymphocyte dicentric radiation bioassay is a 25 cGy photon equivalent dose, which is based on the measurement of 1000 cells per sample⁴⁵. Variations in the background dicentric levels in the general population⁴⁶ demonstrate the effect of confounding factors on the threshold detection level of chromosome aberration based radiation bioassays (Table 5).

DNA damage and DNA mutation :

Ionising radiation causes – single, multiple site damage including strand breaks, base loss, and altered DNA bases

Table 4. A comparison of single cell microgel electrophoresis techniques

Lysis conditions	Electrophoresis conditions	Measurement	Range	Ref.
Neutral (pH 9.5), SDS for 1 h	5 V/cm, 5 min EDTA/SDS	Ratio of fluorescence Number of cones	Gamma rays 0-3 Gy	35
2.5 M NaCl/Triton and Na-sarcosinate (pH 10) for 1 h, 20 min unwinding time	0.83 V/cm, 20-40 min EDTA/NaOH	Tail length	X-rays 0-2 Gy	36, 37
2.5 M NaCl/Triton and Na-sarcosinate (pH 10) for 1h, 20 min unwinding time	0.83 V/cm, 20-40 EDTA/NaOH	tail length	UV light 6-24 J/m ²	38
Alkaline 1 M NaCl for 15 min	5 V/cm, 10 min tris/EDTA	Ratio of head diameter to tail length	0-20 Gy	39
Alkaline 1 M NaCl for 1 h	4 V/cm, 12 min Tris/acetic acid	Tail length, tail moment	X-rays 0-3 Gy 0-15 Gy	40, 68
Neutral pH 8.3 EDTA/SDS at 50°C for 4 h	0.66 V/cm, 12 min tris/acetic acid	Tail moment, tail length	X-rays 0-20 Gy	69
Alkaline pH 10, 2.5 M NaCl/Na-sarcosinate (pH 10) for 5 min	0.83 V/cm, 30 min EDTA/NaOH	Tail length	Gamma rays 0-5 Gy	70
2.5 NaCl/Triton and Na-sarcosinate (pH 10) for 1 h, 40 min unwinding time	0.66 V/cm, 24 min EDTA/NaOH	Tail length	Ultraviolet-C light 0-8 J/m ²	71

and sugar components⁴⁷. However, assays have not been sensitive enough to score accidental, military, environmental or occupational exposure levels. It holds promise for military for acute radiation exposures.

Mutations in nuclear DNA targets have been applied as biomarkers. This assay lacks specificity for detection among individuals that have undergone radiation-induced changes (Table 5).

Much additional research is needed in this area. Mitochondrial DNA changes could help solve the problem. They can potentially be automated to handle large numbers of samples and the information can be quickly conveyed to decision makers.

Gene and protein expression :

Changes in gene and protein expression can be induced by radiation exposure. The sensitivity of the gene expression bioassays appears to be adequate for low radiation doses⁴⁸.

An *in vitro* human peripheral blood lymphocyte model system was used recently to demonstrate that both protein⁴⁹ and gene expression⁵⁰ changes following low dose (>10 cGy) exposure remain elevated for 1 to 3 day, thus providing exposure biomarkers that are potentially better than the non-persistent DNA damage end-points currently used.

This area has great potential for use in the field (Table 5).

Recent radiation detection systems like (i) automated metaphase finder system, (ii) DNA sequence detection system, (iii) Rapid fluorogenic PCR system, (iv) Cepheid's battery operated smart cycler, (v) Hand held biosensor are available for dosimetric purposes.

Practical utility of biomarkers :

In case of accidental radiation exposure in research institutions, industrial radiation installations, radium dial painters, medical institutions where radiodiagnosis is used, all the dosimeters mentioned above will be of immense help for civilian and military population.

In many instances low levels of exposure even dose cause different types of abnormalities (e.g. atomic bomb survivors⁵¹, Chernobyl liquidators and general public exposed to fallout from Chernobyl). Some specific examples of low-level radiation-induced changes that are possible to be detected with sufficient accuracy are :

(i) Changes in ESR in tooth enamel and chromosome aberrations provide a technique that measures dose directly. This has got adequate sensitivity to detect low exposure levels. FT-IR technology has been used for this purpose⁵².

Table 5. Biomarkers of low level radiation exposure

Sl. no.	System	Dose range (cGy)	Minimum detection limit (cGy)	Time for detection	Clinical or medical utility	Ref.
1.	Chromosome aberration, inter phase assays Merit : Sensitive, specific, low back ground level aberration detectable	<25	0.50	5 days	+++	46
	(i) Dicentric and ring Merit : specific	2	0.50	"	+++	45
	(ii) Translocation Merit : specific	6-8	1.00	"	+++	72
	(iii) PCC-FISH metaphase chromosomal aberrations Merit : specific R	10-12		2 days	+++	73
2.	DNA damage					
	(i) Single strand breaks Non-specific	20-50	20	2-3 h	--	47
	(ii) Base damage Non-specific	200-300	200	Few h	++	47
3.	Gene expression/encoded proteins. Non-specific: R	>10		1-3 days		48, 49
	(i) Single R	2		"	+	50
	(ii) Multiple	ND		-	+	49
4.	Lymphocyte depletion kinetics	15	1	8 h	Accident victims ++	42
5.	Differential cytotoxicity	18.9 to	9.75 kBq	-	Human glioma	43
	^{131}I UdR	9.75 kBq	ml^{-1}			
	^{123}I UdR	ml^{-1}				

(+) and (-) indicate positive and negative rank of acceptability; R indicates need for additional research studies.

(ii) Deletion in the long arm of chromosome 2 in mouse by radiation causes acute myelogenous leukemia. Genomic hybridization technique helps in detecting development of leukemias and solid tumors⁴¹.

Practical utility pertaining to radiation casualties and medical treatment decisions in military operation :

The capability to make diagnostic assessments of radiation exposure is needed to support triage of radiation casualties and medical treatment decisions in military operations. The use and development of advanced monitoring and diagnostic technologies compatible with military operations was emphasized. Conventional radiation bioassays require a substantial amount of time between when the sample is taken and when the data can be provided for decision making. These bioassays are evaluated in the laboratories. Detection thresholds can be reduced approximately five-fold by the addition of significant and tiresome scoring efforts. Alternative real time biomarkers that can be measured in field laboratories or with handheld detection devices show promise as screening and clinical diagnostic tools. But they require further development and validation studies.

Clinical factors for predictive assay :

The clinical factors responsible for predictive assay are :

- (i) Total dose and fractionation schedule for same tissue. Similarly, it should be established for different tissues.
- (ii) Acute and late reactions for total dose and fractionated dose.
- (iii) Follow up duration and number of observations per patient.
- (vi) Latency in the development of complications e.g. fibrosis and telangiectasia.
- (v) Treatment factor e.g. volume irradiated, dose distribution, medication, age, anatomical site and life style etc.
- (vi) Homogeneously treated group of patients.
- (vii) Clinical endpoint based on clinical relevance.

Future prospect :

The biomarkes which will be important in future are not necessarily the biochemicals or biopolymers but other technologies namely protein expression profiling (proteomics), single nucleotide polymorphisms, chromosome damage (assessed by cytogenetics⁴⁴, fluorescense *in situ* hybridization⁵³, micronucleus formation), DNA damage (initial DNA damage, residual DNA damage using pulse field gel electrophoresis, alkaline elution, comet assay⁵⁴) and micro array technology for gene expression⁵⁵ are also important.

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References

1. A. L. Brooks, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1999, **75**, 1481.
2. A. L. Brooks, M. A. Khan, R. F. Jostes and F. T. Cross, *J. Toxicol. Environmental Health*, 1993, **40**, 277.
3. W. F. Blakeley, A. L. Brooks, Lt. Col. R. S. Lofis, G. P. V. Sehans and P. Voisin, *Military Medicine*, 2002, **167**, Suppl 1, 20.
4. R. A. Pelroy, "Molecular Biology of Mutational Biomarkers for Human Exposure to Ionising Radiation", NCI, Rockvilly, M.D., 1998.
5. NRC, "Committe on Biological Effects of Ionising Radiations, Health Effects of Exposure to Radon (BEIR VI)", National Academy Press, Washington, D.C., 1998.
6. J. M. Nelson, A. L. Brooks, N. F. Metting, M. A. Khan, R. L. Bushhom, A. Duncan, R. Muck and L. A. Braby, *Radiat. Res.*, 1996, **145**, 568.
7. H. K. Berry, E. L. Saenger, H. Perry, B. I. Friedman, J. G. Kereikes and O. Schall, *Science*, 1963, **142**, 396.
8. G. B. Gerber, G. Gerber, S. Kuruhara, K. I. Altman and O. H. Hempelman, *Radiant. Res.*, 1961, **15**, 314.
9. F. M. Ganis, M. W. Hendrickson and J. W. Howland, *Radiat. Res.*, 1965, **24**, 278.
10. G. B. Gerber, P. Gertler, K. I. Altman and L. H. Hempelman, *Radiat. Res.*, 1961, **15**, 307.
11. H. Smith and A. O. Langlands, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1966, **11**, 487.
12. J. M. D. Borges and B. D. Drujan, *Radiat. Res.*, 1971, **45**, 589.
13. X. C. Le, J. Z. Zing, J. Lee, S. A. Leadon and M. Weinfeld, *Science*, 1998, **280**, 1066.
14. S. Wolff, *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 1998, **106**, 277.
15. A. P. Blanchard and L. Hood, *Nature Biotechnology*, 1996, **14**, 1649.
16. Y. Matsumara, M. Niramatsu and A. Mori, *Neurosciences*, 1985, **11**, 218.
17. S. N. Upadhyay, A. Sharma, K. K. Nagpal and S. K. Saini, *De-fence Science Journal*, 1997, **47**, 383.
18. I. Y. R. Adamson and D.H. Bowden, *Am. J. Pathology*, 1983, **112**, 224.
19. S. N. Upadhyay, *J. Surface Science Technol.*, 2001, **17**, 157.
20. G. M. Floresheim, *Radiat. Res.*, 1993, **133**, 80.
21. R. Pollak and A. J. Febrega, *New England Journal of Medicine*, 1993, **328**, 1851.
22. J. Brooks and R. A. Kanpinen, *Neurochem. Int.*, 1993 **23**, 441.
23. H. C. Goel, S. K. Ganguly, J. Prasad and V. Jain, *Ind. J. Expt. Biol.*, 1996, **34**, 1194.
24. K. B. Tan, T. N. Borun, R. Charpentier, V. J. Cristofello and C. M. Croce, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1982, **257**, 5337.
25. B. D. Strahl and C. D. Allis, *Nature*, 2000, **403**, 41.
26. P. U. Devi and R. Gupta, *J. Radiat. Res.*, 1984, **11**, 166.
27. H. C. Newman, K. M. Prise and B. D. Michael, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 2000, **76**, 1085.
28. V. Ramakrishnan, *Ann. Review. Biophysics. Biomol. Structure*, 1997, **26**, 83.
29. F. A. Myers, D. R. Evans and A. L. Clayton, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2001, **276**, 20197.
30. M. Kozurkova, E. Misurova and K. Kropacova, *Neoplasma*, 1994, **41**, 89.
31. M. Kozurkova, E. Misurova and K. Kropacova, *Mechanisms of Ageing and Development*, 1995, **78**, 1.
32. S. N. Upadhyay, "H₄ Histone as a Potential *in vitro* Biological Dosimeter under Physiological Condition", Paper presented at International Conference on "Emerging Trends in Cancer Research", Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, Vide abstract page number 142, March 14-16, 2002.
33. V. A. Spencer, *Gene*, 1999, **240**, 1.
34. K. N. Prasad, "Handbook of Radiobiology", 2nd. ed., CRC Press, New York, 1998, p. 111.
35. O. Ostling and K. J. Johnson, *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 1984, **123**, 291.
36. N. P. Singh, M. T. McCoy, R. R. Tice and E. L. Schneider, *Experimental Cell Research*, 1998, **175**, 184.
37. N. P. Singh, D. B. Danner, R. R. Tice, J. D. Pearson, L. J. Brant, C. H. Morrel and E. L. Schnider, *Mutation Research*, 1991, **256**, 1.
38. R. R. Tice, P. Andrews and N. P. Singh, *Basic Life Sciences*, 1990, **53**, 291.
39. P. L. Olive, *Radiat. Res.*, 1989, **117**, 79.
40. P. L. Olive, J. P. Banath and R. E. Durand, *Radiat. Res.*, 1990, **122**, 86.
41. M. L. Laramendy, J. Taper, H. Pere, W. El, S. Rifai, V. Hemmer, M. Vasenius, V. Vindegren and Y. Zhu, *Am. J. Pathol.*, 1998, **152**, 1107.
42. R. E. Goans, E. C. Holloway, M. E. Berger and R. C. Ricks, *Health Physics*, 1997, **72**, 513.
43. A. N. Riz, R. J. Mairs, W. G. Angerson, P. D. Stanton, J. R. Reeves, R. Rampling, J. Owens and T. E. Whelden, *British J.*

- Cancer*, 1998, **77**, 385.
44. A. Guerci, F. Dulout and A. Seone, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 2003, **79**, 793.
 45. D. C. Lloyd, A. A. Edwards and A. Leonard, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1992, **61**, 335.
 46. A. Tonomura, K. Kishi and F. Saito. "Types and Frequencies of Chromosomal Aberrations in Peripheral Lymphocytes of General Population". in "Radiation Induced Chromosome Damage in Man", New York, Alan R Liss., 1983, pp. 605-616.
 47. J. F. Ward, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1994, **66**, 427.
 48. S. A. Amundson, K.T. Do and A. J. Formance, *Radiat. Res.*, 1999, **152**, 225.
 49. A. C. Miller, P. G. S. Prasanna, W. F. Blakely, K. P. Hinton and L. Luo, "Radiation-Induced Alterations in the *ras* Signal Transduction Pathway : A Predictive Assay for Biodosimetry Applications", Abstracts of International Conference on "Low-Level Radiation Injury and Medical Countermeasures", Armed Forces Radiobiology Research Institute, Bethesda, M.D., 55, November 8-10, 1999.
 50. S. A. Amudson, K. T. Do and S. Shahab, *Radiat. Res.*, 2000, **154**, 342.
 51. M. P. Little and C. P. Murihold, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1998, **74**, 471.
 52. N. Nakamura, C. Miyazawa, S. Swada and M. Akiyama, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1998, **73**, 619.
 53. M. P. Speicher, S. G. Ballard and D. C. Ward, *Genetics*, 1996, **12**, 368.
 54. J. O. T. Declay and J. L. Moore, *British Journal of Radiology Supplement*, 1992, **24**, 65.
 55. J. M. L. Pierre, V. Caheux, F. Dasilva, N. Callot, N. Harvey, J. Weiss and G. Tachitgia, *Annals of Genetics*, 1998, **41**, 56.
 56. L. H. Hempelmann, H. Lisco and J. G. Hoffman, *Ann. Intern. Med.*, 1952, **36**, 279.
 57. S. N. Upadhyay, R. P. Singh, A. K. Gupta and A. Ghose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 560.
 58. S. N. Upadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 424.
 59. S. N. Upadhyay, *Ind. J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 2001, **38**, 406.
 60. S. N. Upadhyay, R. Bhardwaj, N. K. Chaudhury and T. L. Mathew, "Interaction of Deoxyribonucleic Acid with H₁ Histone in the Un-irradiated and Gamma Irradiated States *in vitro*". Paper presented at International conference on "Radiation Damage and its Modification", LASTEC, Metcalf House, Vide Abstract page No. 31, November 12-15, 2002.
 61. S. N. Upadhyay and T. L. Mathew, *Ind. J. Biochem. Biophys.*, 2000, **37**, 178.
 62. J. B. Little, *Radiat. Res.*, 1970, **44**, 674.
 63. T. Teresima and L. G. Tolmach, *Biophysical J.*, 1963, **3**, 11.
 64. E. E. Beltz, *Cancer Res.*, 1957, **17**, 688.
 65. R. B. Painter and J. E. Cleaver, *Nature (London)*, 1967, **216**, 369.
 66. R. Abrams, *Arch. Biochem.*, 1951, **30**, 90.
 67. R. Bases, F. Mendez and R. Nicolino, *Radiat. Res.*, 1970, **44**, 456.
 68. P. L. Olive, *Journals of the National Cancer Institute*, 1990, **82**, 779.
 69. P. L. Olive, D. Wlodek and J. P. Banath, *Cancer Res*, 1991, **51**, 4671.
 70. J. O. T. Declay, J. L. Moore and S. Mitchell, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1990, **57**, 1268.
 71. M. H. L. Green, J. Lowe, S. A. Harcourt, P. Akinlyyi, T. Rowe, J. Cole, A. V. Austey and C. F. Arlett, *Mutation Research*, 1992, **272**, 137.
 72. L. S. Durm, C. Whitehouse and A. Edwards, *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 2000, **88**, 93.
 73. P. Belgrader, W. Benett and D. Hadley, *Clin. Chem.*, 1998, **44**, 2191.